

Table 1. Length of the first and second leaf blades of 12 rice varieties 10 days after sowing. IRR1, November 1979.

Variety	Length (mm)	
	1st leaf blade	2d leaf blade
<i>Tolerant</i>		
FR13A	60	175
Kurkaruppan	81	147 ^a
Thavalu (15325)	69	168 ^a
Thavalu (15314)	56	183
SML Temerin	62	171 ^a
Nam Sagui 19	63	169
Av	65.2	174.5
<i>Susceptible</i>		
Leb Mue Nahng	111.47	174
T442-57	40	144
IR36	32	118
IR8	42	141
RD7	43	139
IR42	41	142
Av	40.8	143.0

^a Not fully developed leaf.

varieties when compared to the susceptible ones, except Leb Mue Nahng 111. There was a significant correlation between length of the first

leaf blade and percentage of survival ($r = 0.6715^*$). The longer leaf blades made it possible for some leaf tips to be above the water level.

Measurement of the overlapping first leaf sheath showed definitely greater overlapping for the tolerant varieties (Table 2).

The role of overlapping leaf sheaths in submergence tolerance was not clear, but one could surmise that overlapping provided a stiffer culm that prevented plant breakage or collapse at the growing point as the water receded.

There was a high correlation between overlapping of the first leaf sheath and percentage of survival ($r = 0.7261^{**}$).

The width-thickness ratio of the culm showed that the culm of tolerant varieties tended to be circular, and that of the susceptible varieties' slender or flat. There was a correlation between width-thickness ratio of seedling culm and percentage of survival ($r = -0.6450^*$).

The shape of the culm probably was

Table 2. Overlapping of the first leaf sheath at 3 cm above the seed of 10-day-old seedlings. IRR1, December 1979.

Variety	Overlapping (microns)
<i>Tolerant</i>	
FR13A	601
Kurkaruppan	639
Thavalu (15325)	608
Thavalu (15314)	505
SML Temerin	594
Nam Sagui 19	460
Av	568
<i>Susceptible</i>	
Leb Mue Nahng 111	430
T442-57	410
IR36	213
RD7	364
IR42	289
Av	353

responsible also for the degree of overlapping of the leaf sheath or vice versa. There was a high correlation ($r = -0.7384^*$) between the length of overlapping and the width-thickness ratio of the culm. The round culms had more overlapping leaf sheaths than the flat culms. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Temperature tolerance

Variation in chlorophyll of rice seedlings under low temperature

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The normal, green color of rice seedling leaves is a desirable characteristic in areas where low temperature prevails early in the growing season. Low temperature during the early growth stages causes yellowing of leaves and stunting. This study evaluates the effect of low temperature on chlorophyll production. It also correlates chlorophyll production with subsequent expression of leaf discoloration.

Seeds of three cultivars — G. S. 10231 (japonica), CNM20 (a mutant of IR8), and IR8 — were sown at different times so the cultivars were exposed to variable diurnal temperatures of 9.3°C/25.2°C—14.90°C/28.8°C. Samples

for chlorophyll estimation were taken at 30, 60, and 90 days after sowing (DS), and visual ratings for discoloration were recorded.

Chlorophyll estimation was done by following the method described by Yoshida, Forno, Cock, and Gomez (1976). The chlorophyll absorbance on the leaf tissue extract at 645 and 665 m μ were measured by Spectronic-20. The total chlorophyll content was calculated as the sum of chlorophyll "a" and "b" (mg/g fresh wt).

A high value of total chlorophyll content was noted (Table 1) during high temperatures. Total chlorophyll content was gradually reduced with decreasing temperature (22.3°C—9.1°C). But with the age of plants (90 DS), total chlorophyll increased despite lower temperature.

Expression of leaf color did not show a close relationship with total

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chlorophyll in all the cultivars. It has been reported that visual differences in greenness in sorghum do not necessarily mean real differences in chlorophyll content. Lines that are alike may or may not contain the same kind and amounts of chlorophyll. A higher chlorophyll a-b ratio was observed at lower temperature (Table 2), suggesting that the production of chlorophyll 'b' suffered more in a cool environment. ■

Table 1. Variations in total chlorophyll content in 3 cultivars under different temperature regimes. West Bengal, India.^a

Variety	30 DS			60 DS			90 DS		
	Total chlorophyll content (mg/g fresh wt)	Visual rating	Min temp (°C)	Total chlorophyll content (mg/g fresh wt)	Visual rating	Min temp (°C)	Total chlorophyll content (mg/g fresh wt)	Visual rating	Min temp (°C)
CNM20	0.79	1		0.35	7		0.48	7	
G.S. 10231	0.87	1	22.3	0.75	1	17.5	0.49	1	13.7
IR8	0.98	1		1.18	3		0.51	5	
Mean	0.88			0.75			0.49		
CNM20	0.79	1		0.23	7		0.59	7	
G.S. 10231	0.71	1	18.6	0.48	1	14.4	0.68	1	9.5
IR8	0.87	1		0.37	3		0.48	5	
Mean	0.79			0.36			0.58		
CNM20	0.35	3		0.23	7		0.59	7	
G.S. 10231	0.42	1	16.4	0.43	3	12.6	0.66	3	11.2
IR8	0.25	3		0.21	5		0.58	3	
Mean	0.34			0.29			0.61		
CNM20	0.37	7		0.23	7		0.58	3	
G.S. 10231	0.38	3	9.1	0.82	3	12.0	0.84	1	14.7
IR8	0.22	7		0.77	5		0.48	3	
Mean	0.32			0.60			0.63		

^aDS = days after sowing. Visual rating scale: 1 = least or no yellowing, 3 = slight yellowing, 5 = moderate yellowing, and 7 = severe yellowing.

Table 2. Differences in chlorophyll a-b ratio under different temperature regimes.^a

Sowing	30 DS			60 DS			90 DS		
	Mean total chlorophyll content (mg/g fresh wt)	ca:cb	Mean min temp (°C)	Mean total Chlorophyll Content (mg/g fresh wt)	ca:cb	Mean min. temp (°C)	Mean total chlorophyll content (mg/g fresh wt)	ca:cb	Mean min. temp (°C)
7 Oct	0.88	0.97	22.3	0.75	0.98	17.5	0.49	1.36	13.7
22 Oct	0.79	0.72	18.6	0.36	1.32	14.4	0.58	1.24	9.5
7 Nov	0.34	1.53	16.4	0.29	1.25	12.6	0.61	1.19	11.2
22 Nov	0.32	1.32	9.1	0.60	1.35	12.0	0.63	1.20	14.7

^aDS = days after sowing.

Pest management and control DISEASES

Morphological and serological similarities of rice ragged stunt virus samples from China and the Philippines

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The occurrence of rice ragged stunt disease has been reported in China, India, Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines,

Sri Lanka, Taiwan, and Thailand. The disease symptoms are similar in various countries: stunting of plants, appearance of ragged and twisted leaves, formation of vein-swellings, delay in flowering, production of nodal branches, incomplete emergence of panicles, and panicles bearing mostly unfilled grains. The transmission of rice ragged stunt virus (RRSV) by the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* in a persistent manner is also similar.

An early report [IRRN 4(2):12, 1979] noted that the antiserum of RRSV prepared from materials mailed to Italy

from the Philippines reacted positively to diseased materials collected in India, Indonesia, and Thailand when tested by immunoelectron microscopy using the decoration technique.

Recently, diseased materials collected in Guangdong, China [IRRN 4(6): 10, 1979], were examined under an electron microscope and tested by the immunoelectron microscopic techniques of trapping and decoration, and by the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). The antiserum used was prepared with RRSV from the Philippines. Electron microscopy